

**THE IMPORTANCE OF CONTEMPORARY INNOVATIVE
TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN ACADEMIC
ESTABLISHMENTS**

Latipov Bobur Bahrom o'g'li

Qarshi davlat universiteti o'qituvchisi

E-mail: latipovb741@gmail.com

Abstract: This article highlights the importance given to foreign languages in continuing education in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the innovative technologies needed to study them. Teaching English to preschool and primary school children using innovative technology, intellectual games and interactive methods using unusual principles and pedagogical technologies, overcoming difficulties in learning English and becoming stronger the effective use of innovative technologies in the acquisition of knowledge.

Keywords: information and communication technology, pronunciation, language learning, pedagogical experience, "Pantomime", "Story Chain", "Collection of Scholars", "Pictures Speaking".

After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has grown and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. There is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which today are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners.

Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of vocational education. Specialists in various fields have a high level of cooperation with

foreign partners, so they have a high demand for language learning. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of vocational education. Such knowledge is first acquired by people in schools, colleges, high schools, and later in institutes, training courses, or by familiarizing themselves with basic information sets that help them learn a foreign language independently. Today there is a large collection of teaching materials for people with different levels of language skills. New methods and requirements for foreign language teaching in the country have been developed in accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to him, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies.

The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which provides specific concepts and skills. Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language.

The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation,

Grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time.

An important factor in the use of modern technologies in education is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most effective ways. In this process, including: - when using computers, the

student can watch and hear videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language; - It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods; - CD players are available.

The use of these tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of games help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basics of using gaming technology are an activity that activates and accelerates the learner. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express themselves, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize their potential.²

At the heart of any game should be the generally accepted principles and tactics of education. Learning games should be based on the subjects. During the games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and works more comfortably. Students are interested in playful lessons, they strive to win, and the teacher uses them to educate the student. The student is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently.

Today, English teachers use the following innovative methods, based on the experience of educators in the United States and the United States: - "Creative Problem Solving" To use this method, the beginning of the story is read and how it ends. students are referred to the judgment of the students; - Merry Riddles is an important part of teaching English to students, as they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle; - Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson; - “Warm-up exercises” - the use of various games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson - “Pantomime” (pantomime) This method is used in a lesson or written exercise where very difficult topics need to be explained to students. can be used when tired; - A chain story method helps to develop students' oral skills; - Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons. Student can watch and hear videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language.

The use of these tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of games help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basics of using gaming technology are an activity that activates and accelerates the learners’ knowledge. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express themselves, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize their potential.

The student is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English. We know that in the current educational process, the student must be a subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently. In addition to this, English teachers use this method, the beginning of the story is read and how it

ends. Students are referred to the judgment of the students; - Merry Riddles is an important part of teaching English to students, as they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle; - Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and correctly. Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The student strives to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we will contribute to the further development of effective ways for future teachers to effectively use innovative technologies.

References:

1. Karimov I.A. Harmoniously developed generation - the basis of development of Uzbekistan - T: Uzbekistan, 1997
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous democratic state of Uzbekistan - Tashkent. NMI "Uzbekistan", 2017
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people - Tashkent. NMI "Uzbekistan", 2017.
4. "INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN ENGLISH LESSONS" (methodical manual), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages.
5. M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rixsittilayeva. "THE USE OF ASSISTANCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING". Tashkent: Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, 2005
6. O. Hoshimov, I. Yakubov. "METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH" (textbook) Tashkent: Sharq Publishing House, 2003
7. Qurbonov Sh.Y. Seytxalilov Ye.A. Education quality management. - T: Shark.

8. Karimov I.A. Harmoniously developed generation - the basis of development of Uzbekistan - T: Uzbekistan, 1997
9. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Together we will build a free and prosperous democratic state of Uzbekistan - Tashkent. NMI "Uzbekistan", 2017
10. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people - Tashkent. NMI "Uzbekistan", 2017.

Websites

<http://www.ziyonet.uz>

<http://www.pedagog.uz>